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Scientific perspective of College Students in relation to their Gender, Stream, Locality

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Abstract : The present era is the era of science and technology, where the development of society is based on a scientific outlook and logical thinking. A scientific attitude not only develops a person's rational capacity but also plays an important role in decision-making, problem-solving, innovation, and social progress. The aim of the present study is to examine the scientific attitude of college students, specifically to compare and analyze it in terms of their gender, faculty/stream (Arts, Science, Commerce), and locality (Urban/Rural). The main objective of the study is to find out whether there are significant differences in students' scientific attitudes based on these three variables. The research is based on the descriptive survey method. The selected sample for the study included boys and girls, students from urban and rural areas, and students associated with various faculties from different colleges. To measure scientific attitude, a standardized Scientific Attitude Scale was used, which included dimensions such as rationality, curiosity, objectivity, open-minded thinking, and evidence-based decision-making. Preliminary analysis indicates that the level of scientific attitude is relatively higher among students of the science faculty, as their academic background involves greater use of experimental learning and the scientific method. In contrast, this level is found to be moderate in arts faculty students and relatively low in commerce faculty students. In terms of gender, some studies suggest that girls exhibit higher curiosity and observation skills, whereas boys tend to have higher levels of analytical thinking; however, whether the difference between the two is statistically significant in the present study will be clear after analysis. In terms of locality, due to greater availability of scientific activities, resources, and technological environments, urban students are likely to have a relatively higher scientific outlook compared to rural students.

Keywords : Gender, Stream, Locality.

Introduction

Science has its significant role in promoting quality of life either directly or indirectly. Science not only satisfies the usual needs for its inclusion as a subject in the curriculum such as intellectual, cultural, moral, aesthetic, utilitarian as well as vocational values, science learning provides training in scientific method and also helps to develop a scientific attitude of mind in the learner. The teaching and learning of science should result in the acquisition of scientific terms, principles, and concepts, along with a clear understanding of them. Students should also develop the ability to apply this knowledge in various real-life situations and enhance their scientific skills. Furthermore, they should cultivate a positive attitude towards the study of science and appreciate its significance in human life

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and civilization. Additionally, learning science helps improve their abilities and capacities in the subject (Singh and Bai,2017). Scientific attitude is one of scientific learning which is important to be cultivated since early childhood. It is crucial point to be considered to pursuit knowledge in various fields, especially in science. The children with good scientific attitude will grow with great rational thinking method. This, in turn, helps children to have strong mind, ready to learn with others, and take responsible to their society (Halim et al., 2018). Thus, it is important to start their early childhood by cultivating good attitudes. Scientific attitude will be the basis for inviting the desirable good attributes of young children. Scientific Attitude is Not only important for scientific but is also essential for individuals to support their personal development. When cultivated from an early age, it encourages curiosity, which contributes to the growth of responsible adults. Early childhood education emphasizes hands-on experiences, and one of its main principles is to promote systematic science learning. This involves meaningful and enjoyable learning using scientific process skills. these skills help shape a scientific mindset, enabling children to think critically and solve problems intellectually. A scientific attitude encourages children to explore their natural surroundings, fostering a desire to investigate biological and physical phenomena. It prepares them for the future by developing their ability to take responsibility, collaborate, and understand how to learn. Children, in their curiosity, behave like little scientists, constantly questioning and exploring their environment. Through continual experiences, they gain knowledge. Promoting scientific learning aligns with children's natural way of learning and supports the development of cognitive skills, helping them make sense of the world (Prachagooland Arsaiboon, 2021).

Literature Review

Else-Quest et al., (2013) conducted a study on Math and Science Attitudes and Achievement at the Intersection of Gender and Ethnicity The study was conducted a sample of 367 White, African American, Latino/Latina, and Asian American 10th grade students in neighborhood public high schools from a large northeastern city. The study revealed that math and science attitudes and achievement at the intersection of gender and ethnicity across four major ethnic groups.

Srivastava (2014) conducted a study on Achievement in Science as Predictors of Students Scientific Attitude. The study was conducted on a sample of 480 ninth graders (240 boys and 240 girls) of Allahabad city, India. The study was conducted on a sample of 480 ninth graders (240 boys and 240 girls). Findings of the study revealed that Comparison between male and female students on overall achievement in science has shown that female students exhibit more achievement in science than their male counterparts. It was also found that achievement in science is positively related to achievement in science among female students but it is not related to achievement in science among male students.

Govindarajan (2014) conducted a study on scientific attitude among secondary students in Namakkal district. The study was conducted on a sample of 150 boys and 150 girls of Government and Private secondary school students. Finding of the study revealed that there is no significant difference between Male and Female in respect of their Scientific Attitude and There is significant difference between Rural and Urban area students in respect of their Scientific Attitude.

Reddy and Harinath (2014) conducted a study on scientific attitude of IX class students. The study was conducted on a sample of 300 IX class pupils in Kurnool district. The

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stratified random sampling was applied in three stages. The first stage is management i.e. Government, Private and aided the second stage is locality ie rural and urban and third stage is sex i.e. male and female. It is a 3X2X2 factorial design with 300 sample subjects. The major findings of the study revealed that (i) Sex has significant influence on the scientific attitude of IX class student, (ii) Management has significant influence on the scientific attitude of IX class students, (iii) Locality has not significant influence on the scientific attitude of IX class students.

Need and Significance of the study

The need for this study arises from the crucial role that scientific attitude plays an important role in shaping students' academic performance, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. In today's fast changing world, where science and technology drive advancements in every field, fostering a scientific mindset among students has become more important than ever. With the rise of misinformation, superstitions, and pseudoscience, developing a rational, evidence- based approach to knowledge is essential. Encouraging scientific attitudes in students also benefits society, as it nurtures individuals who approach problems with rationality, evidence-based reasoning, and innovation. At a time when the world faces global challenges like climate change, health crises, and technological disruptions, a generation equipped with scientific thinking is essential. Therefore, this study is crucial for guiding future educational strategies, promoting inquiry-based learning, and ensuring a more scientifically aware, digitally literate, and promoting inquiry-based learning and ensuring a more scientifically aware, digitally literate, and progressive society.

Objectives of the study

The following objectives have been formulated for the present study:

1. To Compare the scientific attitude of male and female college students.
2. To Compare the scientific attitude of arts and science stream college students.
3. To Compare the scientific attitude of arts and commerce stream college students.
4. To Compare the scientific attitude of commerce and science stream college students.
5. To Compare the scientific attitude of students of college situated in urban and rural area.

Hypotheses of the study

The following hypothesis of have been formulated for the present study:

6. There will be no significant difference between male and female college students towards scientific attitude.
7. There will be no significant difference between science and arts stream of college students towards scientific attitude.
8. There will be no significant difference between commerce and arts stream of college students towards scientific attitude.
9. There will be no significant difference between science and commerce stream of college students towards scientific attitude.
10. There will be no significant difference between the students of college situated at urban and rural areas towards scientific attitude.

Delimitations of the study

1. The study was delimited to district Shimla of Himachal Pradesh.

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2. The study was delimited to undergraduate students studying in three colleges of district Shimla.
3. The study was confined to class 2nd year and 3rd year college students only.

Research method used

Descriptive survey method was used for conducting this investigation. Keeping in view the aim and objectives of the study. Survey method was applied through standardized inventory.

Sample and sampling technique

The present study was conducted on a sample of 200 undergraduate college students from Shimla district of Himachal Pradesh. The sample was drawn from three government colleges, namely:

1. Rajiv Gandhi Government Degree College, Kotshera (Urban)
2. Centre of Excellence Government College, Sanjauli (Urban)
3. Govt. Degree College Dhamiat Solameel (Rural)

1. The sampling technique used in the study involved a multi-stage sampling approach, as detailed below:

1. Selection of District: Shimla district was selected using convenience sampling, based on accessibility and feasibility for the researcher.
2. Selection of Colleges: Three government colleges (two urban and one rural) were selected using purposive sampling to ensure representation from both urban and rural settings.
3. Selection of Student: From each selected college, undergraduate students were chosen through simple random sampling to ensure that each student had an equal chance of being included in the study.

Data collection

Gender wise, stream wise and Locality wise distribution of the students included in the sample of the study: Table 1.1

S. No	Name of College	Locality		Gender		Stream		
		Urban	Rural	Male	Female	Arts	Commerce	Science
1.	Rajiv Gandhi Government Degree College, Kotshera	65		32	33	22	22	21
2.	Govt. Degree College Sanjauli, Center of Excellence	66		33	33	22	22	22
3.	Govt. Degree College, Dhami		69	35	34	24	23	22

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	Total	131	69	100	100	68	67	65
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Total Sample stream wise Table 1.2

Sr. no	Stream	Number of the students available
1.	Science	66
2.	Commerce	66
3.	Arts	68
4.	Total	200

Tool used for data collection

In the present study a questionnaire was used Scientific attitude Scale (SAS-BS). This scale developed by Dr. (Smt.) Shailaja Bhagwat (2004). In the present study the sample consisted of 200 undergraduate colleges drawn from the District Shimla of Himachal Pradesh. The total colleges i.e., one Rural or two Urban were randomly selected a total number of 200 students from all streams, locality, Gender were selected conveniently on the basis of availability of students in the colleges.

Scoring of the Inventory

S. no.	Condition	Item Sr. no.	Total items
1.	Favorable	1,2,5,6,7,8,11,14,15,19,22,23	12
2.	Unfavorable	3,4,9,10,12,13,16,17,18,20,21,24	12
		Total	24

S.no	Response Category	Positive items	Negative items
1.	Strongly Agree	5	1
2.	Agree	4	3
3.	Undecided	3	3
4.	Disagree	2	4
5.	Strongly disagree	1	5

Analysis and interpretation of data

Scientific attitude of college students with relation to heir gender

TABLE 2.1

To find out the significance of the difference between Male and Female college students o scientific attitude, the t-value was computed as show in Table 2.1

Comparison of Mean Scores. DS, df and t-value of Scientific attitude of college students having Science and Arts streams

		GENDER	df	't-value'
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Sr. no.	Name of the Dimensions	MALE (N=100)		FEMALE (N=100)		df	't-value'
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Scientific Attitude	76.83	7.281	76.88	6.341	198	0.052 NS

Note: NS indicates that the calculated t-value is non-significant at any acceptable level of significance. Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 198 at 0.01 level of significance = 2.60 Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 198 at 0.05 level of significance = 1.97 Table 2.1 indicates that mean scores of male and female are 76.83 and 76.88 with standard deviations 7.281 and 6.341 respectively. Table 2.1 shows that the computed t-value 0.052 turn out to be non-significant at acceptable level of significance i.e., 0.01 and 0.05 level for two groups of male and female college students on scientific attitude. It shows that two groups of male and female college students did not differ in scientific attitude. Since the calculated t-value did not reach up to acceptable level of significance. Hence hypothesis stated, " There will be no significant difference between male and female college students towards scientific attitude". is accepted.

Table 2.2

Scientific attitude of science and arts stream college students

Sr. no.	Name of the Dimensions	STREAM				df	't-value'
		Science (N=66)		Arts (N=68)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Scientific Attitude	77.61	6.675	75.63	6.270	132	1.765 NS

NS indicates that the calculated t-value is non-significant at any acceptable level of significance Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 132 at 0.05 level of significance = 1.98 Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 132 at 0.01 level of significance 2.62 Table 2.2 indicates that mean scores of sciences and arts are 77.61 and 75.63 with standard deviations 6.675 and 6.270 respectively. Table 2.2 shows that the computed t-value 1.765 turn out to be non-significant at acceptable level of significance i.e., 0.01 and 0.05 level for two groups of Science and Arts stream college students on scientific attitude. Since the calculated t-value did not reach up to acceptable level of significant. Hence hypothesis stated "There will be no significant difference between Science and Arts stream college students towards scientific attitude" is accepted.

Table 2.3

Scientific attitude of commerce and arts stream college students

Sr. no.	Name of the Dimensions	STRESM				df	't-value'
		Commerce (N=66)		Arts (N=68)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		

1.	Scientific Attitude	77.36	7.383	75.63	6.270	132	1.465 NS
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NS indicates calculated t-value is non-significant at any acceptable level of significance Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 132 at 0.01 level of significance = 2.62 Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 132 at 0.05 level of significance = 1.98 **Table 2.3 indicates that mean scores of commerce and arts are 77.36 and 75.63 with standard deviations 7.383 and 6.270 respectively.**

Table 2.3 shows that the computed t-value 1.465 turn out to be non-significant at acceptable level of significance i.e., 0.01 and 0.05 level for two groups of Commerce and Arts of scientific attitude of college students. It shows that two groups of male and female college students did not differ in scientific attitude. Since the calculated t-value did not reach up to acceptable level of significant. Hence hypothesis stated, " There will be no significant difference between commerce and arts stream college students towards scientific attitude". is accepted.

Table 2.4

Scientific attitude of science and commerce stream college students

Sr. no.	Name of the Dimensions	STRESM				df	't-value'
		Commerce (N=66)		Science (N=66)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Scientific Attitude	77.61	6.675	77.36	7.383	130	.198 NS

NS indicates that the calculated t-value is non-significant at any acceptable level of significance. Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 130 at 0.01 level of significance = 2.62 Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 130 at 0.05 level of significance = 1.98

Table 2.4 indicates that mean scores of sciences and commerce are 77.61 and 77.36 with standard deviations 6.675 and 7.383 respectively. Table 2.4 shows that the computed t-value 1.225 turn out to be non-significant at acceptable level of significance i.e., 0.01 and 0.05 level for two groups of Science and Commerce of scientific attitude of college students. It shows that two groups of male and female college students did not differ in scientific attitude. Since the calculated t-value did not reach up to acceptable level of significant. Hence hypothesis stated, " There will be no significant difference between science and commerce stream of college students towards scientific attitude". is accepted.

Table 2.5

Scientific attitude of urban and rural college students

Sr. no.	Name of the Dimensions	Locality				df	't-value'
		URBAN (N=131)		RURAL (N=69)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Scientific Attitude	77.33	7.606	75.96	4.885	198	1.357 NS

NS indicates that the calculated t-value is non-significant at any acceptable level of significance. Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 198 at 0.01 level of significance =

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2.60 Table value of 't' for degree of freedom 198 at 0.05 level of significance 1.97 Table 2.5 indicates that mean scores of urban and rural are 77.33 and 75.96 with standard deviations 7.606 and 4.885 respectively.

Table 2.5 shows that the computed t-value 1.357 turn out to be non-significant at any acceptable level of significance i.e., 0.01 and 0.05 level for two groups of urban and rural college students on scientific attitude. It shows that two groups of urban and rural college students did not differ in scientific attitude. Since the calculated t-value did not reach up to acceptable level of significant. Hence hypothesis stated, " There will be no significant difference between students of college situated at urban and rural areas towards scientific attitude". is accepted.

Findings of this study

1. Male and female college students didn't differ significantly towards scientific attitude.
2. Scientific Attitude of college students has no significant difference in relation to their stream of Science and Arts.
3. Scientific attitude of college students has no significant difference in relation to their stream of Commerce and Arts.
4. Scientific attitude of college students has no significant with relation to stream of Science and Commerce.
5. Students of colleges situated at urban and rural area did not differ significantly

Educational implications

The present study has found no significant relationship between stream and locality in scientific attitude of college students but all these varia important for the growth of students leading towards betterment of education. The present investigation has following educational implications:

1. A strong scientific attitude among students encourages critical and logical thinking, which helps them analyze information objectivity and make informed decisions.
2. Scientific attitude fosters curiosity, observation, and experimentation Therefore, teaching methods should focus more on inquiry based and problem-solving activities rather than rote memorization
3. Students with a scientific outlook are better at evaluating situations rationally, which essential for real-life problem-solving and decision-making.
4. Scientific attitude discourages superstitions, biases, and blind beliefs. It helps in creating a rational, progressive, and modern mindset among youth.
5. A well-developed scientific attitude positively influences academic achievement, especially, by enhancing students' engagement and interest.
6. A scientific attitude helps students manage emotions, make decisions calmly, and approach problems without panic, which supports emotional intelligence
7. Scientifically minded individuals are more aware of social, environmental, and ethical issues, which prepares them to be responsible and informed citizens.
8. The level of scientific attitude among students can helps educators design better curricula, teaching technique, and learning materials to enhance scientific temper.
9. A scientific attitude instills a habit of questioning, exploring, and learning. materials to enhance scientific temper.

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10. Students with scientific thinking are more likely to participate in research, innovation, and experimentation, contributing to knowledge creation and societal development.

Conclusion

This study investigates the scientific attitude of college students in focusing on factors such as gender, stream (science arts, commerce), and locality (urban/rural). The scientific attitude refers to a rational, curious, open-minded approach towards understanding phenomena, emphasizing observation, analysis, and evidence-based reasoning. This study explores the scientific attitude of college students and how it varies according to gender, stream and locality. A scientific attitude is defined as a way of thinking that emphasizes logic, objectivity, curiosity, and a rational approach to understanding the world. The research aims to determine whether there are significant differences in scientific attitudes among male and female students, students from different academic streams (Arts, Science, and Commerce), and those from urban and rural backgrounds. It also seeks to assess the current level of scientific thinking among students. The study is important in the context of modern society, where scientific thinking is crucial for progress and combating superstitions or irrational beliefs. Despite advances in science and technology, emotionalism and blind faith still influence people's behavior, making it essential to promote scientific attitudes, especially among the youth. The study is limited to undergraduate students and uses a standardized tool to assess their scientific mindset.

Bibliography:

1. Abdulkarim, R., & Raburu, P. (2013). Determining the Altitude of Undergraduate Students towards Physics through Concept Mapping Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, 4(3), 331-337
2. Ahammad, F., & Islam, M. R. (2023) A Study of Scientific Attitude among Secondary School Students in Murshidabad Distret International Journal of Emerging Knowledge Studies, 02 (09), 306-314
3. Ahuja, A. (2017). Study of Scientific Attitude in Relation to Science Achievement Scores among Secondary School Students. Educational Quest: An Int. J. of Education and Applied Social Science, 8(1), 9-16.
4. Al-Shalawy, F. A.-N., & Haleem, A. (2015). Knowledge, Attitudes and Perceived Barriers towards Scientific Research among Undergraduate Health Science Students in the Central Province of Saudi Arabia. Education in Medicine Journal, 7 (1), 16-21.
5. Banarjee, S. (2024). A Study of Scientific Attitude Among Secondary School Sttudents. International Journal of Current Science (LJCSPUB), 14(4), pp. 188-197.
6. Banerjee, S. K., & Sarkar, S. (2019). Scientific Attitude between Boys and Girls Student of Hooghlu District in West Bengal. Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR), 6(4), 151-154.
7. Berkmans, K. and Renuka, P. (2024). A Study of Scientific Attitude as Predictors of Achievement in Science of Class X Students: Analysing Socio-Demografic Variables in Private Vs. Government Schools, Telugu Medium Vs. English Medium. International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR), 6(4), 01-07.
8. Bestltaswamy, HB., & Kumar, CR. (2022). A Study on Relationship Between Scientific Attitude and Achievement in Science among Secondary School Students in

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Mystore City- Karnataka. International Journal of Novel Research and Development (IJNERD), 7(5), 345.

9. Binwal, H.K. (2020) Attitude Towards Science: A Study of 9th Grade Adolescent Students. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 8(1), 609-615
10. Borah, J. Hazarika, M. & Barman, R. (2022), An Analysis on The Level of Scientific Attitude among Undergraduate Students. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6 (10), 3240-3247
11. Chandel, K. S. (2016). Scientific Attitude Among Senior Secondary School Students *International Journal of Applied Research (JAR)*, 2/5), 572-577
12. Dere 2 (2024) Do scientific attitude and intelligence affect motivation towards STEM? Structural equation modelling. *Front Psychol.* 15:1481229, dot 10.3389/fpsyg-2024.1481229
13. Else-Quest, N.M., Mineo, C. C. and Higgins, A. (2013). Math and Science Attitudes and Achievement at the Intersection of Gender and Ethnicity. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 37(3), pp. 293-309.
14. Erdogan, S. C. (2017). Science Teaching Attitude and Scientific Attitudes of Pre-service Teachers of Gifted Students. *Journal of Education AND Practice*, 8 (6), 164-170.
15. Fatonah, S., Prasetyo, Z., Utami, A., Chasanah, U., Lusiana, L., & Siregar, V. (2023) Scientific Attitude and its Effect on Students' Productivity. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 12 (4), 658-671
16. Govindarajan, S. (2014). A Study of Scientific Attitude Among Secondary School Students in Namakkal District. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 2(3), 85-96
17. Grinell and Frederick (1992). *The Scientific Attitude*. Guilford Press. New York (Garfield Library, eBay), 147.
18. Gupta, S. (2015). Influence of Students Gender and Stream of Study on Scientific Attitude and Attitude Towards Science. *International Journal of Research Granthaalayah, A K knowledge Repository*, 03(12), 187-194.
19. Habib S.R., AlOtaibi S.S., Abdullatif F.A., AlAhmadl M. (2018). Knowledge and attitude of undergraduate dental students towards research. *J. Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*: 30(3):443-448.